

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of CO₂-Adsorbing Metal Organic Framework “CALF-20”.

Edgar Contreras* ^{1,2}; Isaac Herraiz ^{1,2}; Enrique Moliner ¹.

1: LOMARTOV S.L. Applied Innovation Engineering. C/Alfarería 3. 46100 Burjassot (Valencia), Spain.

2: Universitat Politècnica de València. Camino de Vera s/n. 46022 Valencia, Spain.

** Corresponding author. Edgar Contreras: econtreras@lomartov.com*

ABSTRACT

Calgary Framework-20 (CALF-20) is a zinc-based metal organic framework (MOF) with high water stability and excellent CO₂ adsorption properties. Several studies have proven CALF-20 to reach optimal performance in CO₂ capture from air with several N₂/CO₂ compositions. Currently, the European Project “SOLDAC” tests and implements different morphologies of CALF-20 for the Direct Air Capture unit of its breakthrough CO₂-to-ethylene solar conversion technology. In an effort to maintain the implementation of CALF-20 for CO₂ capture as environmentally responsible as possible, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is performed. The aim of the LCA is to determine the overall environmental impacts associated with the synthesis of CALF-20, tracking them from the extraction of raw materials, through the synthesis of precursors, to the final synthesis of the MOF. Implementing this environmental screening approach allows for comprehensive and environmentally aware decision-making when developing CALF-20-enabled technologies.

KEYWORDS: Metal-organic framework CALF-20; Life cycle assessment; Direct air capture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Calgary Framework 20 (CALF-20) is a metal-organic framework (MOF) comprised of a crystallographic arrangement of two-dimensional zinc(II) triazolate grids pillared by oxalate anions perpendicular to the layers, creating a three-dimensional porous structure with no open coordination sites.

CALF-20 has shown the ability to take up 4.07 mmol/g at conditions of 1.2 bar and 20°C with a CO₂/N₂ selectivity of 230, by ideal adsorbed solution theory, for a 10:90 CO₂/N₂ mixture. Additionally, it showed low water-affinity and sustained CO₂ capacity up to and above a relative humidity of 40%, making it favorable for direct air capture applications (Lin et al., 2021).

Studies on the binding sites of CALF-20 for guest molecules show that CO₂ has its most probable binding in the middle of the framework's pores, with interatomic distances between consistent with physisorption. Furthermore, analysis of the binding energy proved attractive dispersion interactions to contribute in 85% to the CO₂-CALF20 interaction, with electrostatics providing the balance.

However, implementing the use of CALF-20 for said application requires a prior screening of the environmental impacts associated to its synthesis, as doing so allows for a better understanding of the actual alleviation on CO₂ emissions that it enables.

As a response, a life cycle assessment (LCA) on the traditional synthesis of CALF-20 – as reported by Lin et al., 2021 – is presented in this study, aiming to assess its implementation in the European Project “SOLDAC: Solar Direct Air Capture and Conversion” (G.A. 101069359).

The principal aim of the SOLDAC project is to produce sustainable ethylene and ethanol from the electrochemical conversion of atmospheric CO₂ by means a novel technology that supposes the integration of three unit operations – a direct air capture (DAC) unit for the capture, purification,

and compression of the atmospheric CO₂; a photoelectrochemical (PEC) stack for the conversion into ethylene and ethanol; and a full-spectrum solar (FSS) collector to provide the energy and heat duties of the prior two units.

CALF-20 is currently being studied as a potential candidate for the material composition of the nanoporous adsorption beds of SolDAC's direct air capture unit. Consequently, the development of this study is motivated by the need to ensure the environmental responsibility of the project.

2. GOAL AND SCOPE

The intended application of the LCA – and general objective of the study – is to report the environmental impacts of the synthesis of CALF-20 across the complete range of impact categories provided by the employed assessment method, providing a baseline for future environmental screenings on CALF-20-enabled technologies, including the SolDAC project. The target audience for this study is the general scientific community working in the topic.

The system that is being assessed in this study is the manufacturing process of CALF-20 powder for its application as CO₂ adsorbent. The functional unit (FU) of the system is one kilogram of synthesized CALF-20, meaning that all environmental impacts will be determined per unit mass of the assessed material.

Additionally, the boundaries of the system follow a cradle-to-gate approach, meaning that the environmental impacts are determined from the extraction of raw materials (cradle) to the final manufacture of the MOF (gate). This system boundary is fit for the application of the assessment, providing an environmental baseline for CALF-20, because the next phases of its life cycle (i.e., use phase, end-of-life, disposal) are defined by the specific technology where it is to be implemented.

Following the European Commission’s recommendation on “methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organizations” (The European Commission, 2021), the impact assessment method employed in this assessment is Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.0, along with its characterization, weighting, and normalization standards.

Both the modelling of inventories and the impact assessment are performed with the SimaPro 9.2 software. The building of inventories into SimaPro is made using the materials available in the Ecoinvent 3.6 database.

3. LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY (LCI) ANALYSIS

The life cycle inventory (LCI) for the synthesis of one kilogram of CALF-20 was built according to the procedure reported by Lin et al., 2021 and peer-reviewed by partners from the University of St. Andrews. The resulting inventory is presented ahead, in **Table 1**.

Table 1. LCI for the synthesis of one kilogram of CALF-20 powder

Type of input	Input	Quantity	Units
Synthesis precursor	Zinc oxalate dihydrate	950.00	g
Synthesis precursor	1,2,4-triazole	1,404.70	g
Solvent	Methanol	19,782.50	g
Solvent	Water	16,616.67	g
Energy	Heating	20.44	kWh
Type of output	Output	Quantity	Units
Product	CALF-20 powder	1,000.00	g
Waste	Wastewater	37,753.33	g

The data regarding required mass of synthesis precursors and solvents, as well as of obtained product were directly disclosed by the team at University of St. Andrews, while the energy input and wastewater output had to be calculated from the procedure reported by them.

3.1 Calculation of energy input

The energy input was obtained by modelling the consumption of the reported heating needs for the procedure: two sets of heating in a conventional laboratory oven, one at 100 °C for 84h and another at 60°C overnight. The energy consumption of each set was calculated by considering the use of a commercially available laboratory oven with the technical specifications presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Modelled oven specifications.

Concept	Quantity	Unit
Max. Temp.	204	°C
Max. Power	1.2	kW
Max. Load	91	kg

(ITW EAE, 2020)

A linear trend is assumed to determine the power (P) of the oven as a function of its temperature (T) setting, where a power of 0 kW is needed for a 20°C setting and 1.2 kW are needed for a 204°C setting. The resulting function – illustrated in **Figure 1** – is obtained as follows, using the definition of a slope:

$$P = mT + b$$

$$m = \frac{P_2 - P_1}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{1.2 - 0}{204 - 20} = \frac{3}{460}$$

$$P = \frac{3}{460}T - \frac{3}{23}$$

Figure 1. Function for power determination from oven’s temperature setting.

Applying the obtained function, the power for both heating sets were calculated and then multiplied by their corresponding heating times to obtain the energy of each set. However, because these sets are considered to be made at the oven’s full load, the resulting energy values were divided by its load capacity to obtain a “mass-specific” energy consumption value per set. Finally, said value is multiplied by the actual load of the oven, according to the mass inputs of the inventory. All values are presented in **Table 3**.

The sum of the actual energy consumption for both heating sets results in a total energy input of 20.44 kWh, as reported in **Table 1**.

Table 3. Energy consumption data per heating set

Concept	Set 1	Set 2
Temp. setting [°C]	100	60
Estimated power [kW]	0.522	0.261
Heating time [h (s)]	84 (302,400)	16 (57,600)
Estimated energy [kJ]	157,773.913	15,026.087
Full load capacity [g]	91,000	91,000
Mass-specific consumption [kJ/g]	1.734	0.165
Actual load [g]	38,753.33	38,753.33
Actual energy consumption [kJ]	67,189.726	6,399.022

3.2 Calculation of wastewater

The mass of generated wastewater was calculated by a mass balance, subtracting the mass of produced CALF-20 powder from the total mass of material inputs, resulting in 37,753 g; as reported in **Table 1**.

3.3 Modelling of precursors

Both synthesis precursors – 1,2,4-triazole and zinc oxalate dihydrate – are not readily available in the Ecoinvent database for direct input when modelling the LCI for the synthesis of CALF-20 in SimaPro. Consequently, both precursors must be previously modelled from their respective synthesis procedures, enabling their later input into the final LCI of the CALF-20 synthesis.

1,2,4-triazole was modelled from the synthesis procedure reported in patent US4267347A, issued to Petree et al., 1981. This patent claims a method for its direct preparation from hydrazine and formamide, precursors that are readily available in the Ecoinvent database.

A process flow diagram (PFD) of the synthesis procedure – presented in **Figure 2** – was built from the claims of the patent, adjusted to the production of 1 kg of 1,2,4-triazole. The material inputs and outputs of the process were calculated according to the stoichiometry and the yields of reaction and purification reported in the patent.

Mass balances:

Stream #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Temperature [°C]	25	25	25	170	130	107.5	107.5	117.5	117.5
Vapor fraction	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Mass flowrate [kg]	0.77	2.14	2.79	3.55	1.06	1.89	1.89	0.66	0.66
Flowrates [mol]									
1,2,4-triazole				14.95	14.49275	0.31	0.31	0.149512	0.149512
Water	15.48783			29.90		29.90	29.90	0	0
Ammonia				29.90		29.90	29.90	0	0
Formic Acid				14.95		14.95	14.95	0	0
Hydrazine	15.48783			0.54		0.54	0.54	0	0
Formamide		47.49	61.95	17.10		2.63	2.63	14.46284	14.46284
Flowrates [kg]									
1,2,4-triazole	0	0	0	1.031635	1	0.021318	0.021318	0.010316	0.010316
Water	0.278781	0	0	0.538244	0	0.538244	0.538244	0	0
Ammonia	0	0	0	0.508342	0	0.508342	0.508342	0	0
Formic Acid	0	0	0	0.687756	0	0.687756	0.687756	0	0
Hydrazine	0.495611	0	0	0.017171	0	0.017171	0.017171	0	0
Formamide	0	2.136982	2.787809	0.769394	0	0.118566	0.118566	0.650828	0.650828
Unit									
	R-101	T-101	E-101	E-102					
Energy duty [kWh]	0.96	0.87	3.22	2.95					

2,9,3 node
 INPUTS 2.798 kg
 OUTPUTS 2.788 kg
Reactor
 INPUTS 3.562 kg
 OUTPUTS 3.553 kg
Distillator
 INPUTS 3.553 kg
 OUTPUTS 3.616 kg
Overall balance
 INPUTS 2.911 kg
 OUTPUTS 2.955 kg

Substance	M.W.
1,2,4-triazole	69
Water	18
Ammonia	17
Formic Acid	46
Hydrazine	32
Formamide	45

Figure 2. PFD for the synthesis of 1,2,4-triazole according to pat. USA4267347A.

Meanwhile, the energy inputs were determined considering the requirements of the process related to: (1) the energy duty of the reactor, and (2) the energy required for the separation and isolation of 1,2,4-triazole from the reactor's output solution.

These were calculated with the temperatures reported by the patent for each stage of the synthesis, as well as with the specific properties of the different materials involved.

Firstly, the energy duty of the reactor was determined by calculating the heat of reaction associated with the synthesis of triazole, following **equation 1**.

$$\Delta H_{rxn} = \sum n_j \cdot [\Delta \hat{H}_{f_j}^o + C_{p_j} \cdot (T_{out} - 298K)] - \sum n_i \cdot [\Delta \hat{H}_{f_i}^o + C_{p_i} \cdot (T_{in} - 298K)] \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Symbol	Meaning	Units
$i ; j$	Input species; output species	-
ΔH_{rxn}	Heat of reaction	kJ
n	Moles	Mol
$\Delta \hat{H}_f^o$	Standard heat of formation	kJ · mol ⁻¹
C_p	Specific heat capacity	kJ · mol ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹
$T_{out} ; T_{in}$	Outflow reaction temperature; feedstock temperature	K

On the other hand, the energy for purification was calculated in two parts: the heating requirement for the distillation of the reactor's output solution, following **equation 2**; and the refrigeration requirement for the condensation of the obtained distillate, according to **equation 3**.

$$\Delta H_{dist.} = n \cdot [\bar{C}_p \cdot (T_{ovh.} - T_{in}) + \Delta \bar{H}_{vap}] \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$\Delta H_{cond.} = n \cdot \Delta \bar{H}_{vap} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Symbol	Meaning	Units
$\Delta H_{dist.}$	Heat requirement for distillation	kJ
$\Delta H_{cond.}$	Refrigeration to condensate distillates	kJ
n	Moles of output reaction solution	Mol
\bar{C}_p	Average specific heat of reaction solution	kJ · mol ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹
$T_{ovh.} ; T_{in}$	Overhead distillation temp.; initial solution temp.	K
$\Delta \bar{H}_{vap}$	Average latent heat of reaction solution	kJ · mol ⁻¹

All calculated energy demands were adjusted to account for the scaling-up to an industrial process by applying the correction factors used by (Cuéllar-Franca et al., 2016), who performed a similar model of the same synthesis procedure based on patent US4267347A as well. The correction

factors have values of 4.2 for heating (assuming the use of natural gas) and 3.2 for cooling (assuming the use of electricity for refrigeration equipment).

The resulting inventory, presented in **Table 4**, enabled modeling 1,2,4-triazole as a new material in SimaPro. The outputs correspond to the mass of produced 1,2,4-triazole and the “average wastewater treatment” item available in Ecoinvent. The wastewater volume was obtained by calculating an average density of stream 7 in the PFD and multiplying it times the total mass of the stream.

Table 4. Inventory for the production of 1 kg of 1,2,4-triazole.

Type of input	Input	Quantity	Units
Synthesis precursor	Hydrazine	495.61	g
Synthesis precursor	Formamide	2,136.98	g
Solvent	Water	278.78	g
Energy	Reaction heat	0.96	kWh
Energy	Purification energy	7.05	kWh
Type of output	Output	Quantity	Units
Product	1,2,4-triazole	1,000.00	g
Waste	Wastewater	2,114.59	mL

On the other hand, the inventory for the synthesis of the second precursor of CALF-20, **zinc oxalate dihydrate**, was built based on the experimental procedure reported by Qi et al., 2014.

The procedure described in the study states that equimolar parts of zinc oxide and oxalic acid dihydrate are mixed, milled, and then aged for 7 days, obtaining a molar equivalent of zinc oxalate. All the procedure is carried out in solid phase, with no solvents, and a 100% reaction yield is assumed for the sake of this study.

To calculate the energy demand of the milling process, the technical specifications of an industrial batch ball mill were consulted. The selected mill, from HengXing Engineering, reported a nominal power of 2.2 kW with a nominal load capacity of 200 kg (HengXing Engineering, n.d.).

In order to scale the power demand per unit mass, a specific power was calculated by dividing the nominal power over the nominal load capacity, giving a value of 0.011 kW/kg. This value was then used to calculate the adjusted electricity demand for an assumed milling time of 3 hours and a load of one kilogram.

The resulting inventory is presented in **Table 5**. Both reaction precursors are available in the Ecoinvent database, making it possible to model zinc oxalate in SimaPro using this inventory.

Table 5. Inventory for the production of 1 kg of zinc oxalate.

Type of input	Input	Quantity	Units
Synthesis precursor	Zinc oxide	429.54	g
Synthesis precursor	Oxalic acid dihydrate	665.42	g
Energy	Mill electric consumption	0.03	kWh
Type of output	Output	Quantity	Units
Product	Zinc oxalate dihydrate	1,000.00	g

However, when looking into the model prepared by Ecoinvent of the zinc oxide precursor, it came up that no elemental flow of zinc was considered for its composition; meaning that virtually, there is no actual zinc in the Ecoinvent model of zinc oxide. This is relevant and non-neglectable for the scope of the study as zinc accounts for the metallic part of the CALF-20 metal-organic framework, which is fundamental to its characterization; this is especially true for any future work that takes on the reported impacts from this study to compare CALF-20 with other MOFs for similar applications.

To account for this situation, the “elemental zinc” item from the Ecoinvent database was implemented as a substitute (proxy) for zinc oxalate in the LCI for the synthesis of CALF-20. To determine the mass of elemental Zn to be considered in the inventory, the mass fraction of elemental zinc within zinc oxalate dihydrate was determined by dividing the mass of one mole of Zn over the mass of one mole of Zinc oxalate dihydrate (as there is one atom of Zn per molecule of Zn oxalate). The obtained fraction – 0.3453 – was then multiplied by the total mass of zinc oxalate in the inventory for the standard synthesis of one kilogram of CALF-20, which has a value of 950.00 g, as reported in **Table 1**. The resulting inventory after implementing these changes is presented in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Corrected LCI for the synthesis of one kilogram of CALF-20 powder

Type of input	Input	Quantity	Units
Synthesis precursor	Zinc oxalate dihydrate	328.04	g
Synthesis precursor	1,2,4-triazole	1,404.70	g
Solvent	Methanol	19,782.50	g
Solvent	Water	16,616.67	g
Energy	Heating	20.44	kWh
Type of output	Output	Quantity	Units
Product	CALF-20 powder	1,000.00	g
Waste	Wastewater	37,753.33	g

4. LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Based on its LCI, the impacts for the synthesis of CALF-20 across all categories offered by the EF3.0 methodology were assessed. **Table 7** presents the calculated impacts disaggregated by the contribution of each input/output of the inventory to the total impact. These values are shaded with a color scale per category, where red represents the highest value, and green the lowest. Impact categories have been abbreviated as indicated in the table footer.

Table 7. Impact reporting for the synthesis of CALF-20.

Impact category	Unit	Share of impact per input/output						Total impact
		1,2,4-triazole	Zinc oxalate	Methanol	Deionised water	Electricity	Wastewater	
CC	kg CO _{2,eq}	22.87	0.86	13.36	4.2E-03	7.68	0.01	44.78
OD	kg CFC11 _{eq}	5.5E-06	6.1E-08	4.4E-06	1.1E-09	4.7E-07	4.8E-10	1.0E-05
IR	kBq U-235 _{eq}	1.04	0.09	0.16	1.9E-04	1.52	7.0E-04	2.82
Ph	kg NMVOC _{eq}	0.04	0.01	0.04	1.1E-05	0.02	4.3E-05	0.10
PM	disease inc.	6.2E-07	4.0E-08	1.8E-07	3.0E-10	9.7E-08	8.1E-10	9.5E-07
HT-NC	CTUh	3.9E-07	1.5E-07	7.6E-08	1.6E-10	6.3E-08	3.8E-09	6.9E-07
HT-C	CTUh	4.0E-09	5.0E-09	2.2E-09	1.7E-12	1.5E-09	6.2E-11	1.3E-08
Ac	mol H ⁺ _{eq}	0.08	0.01	0.05	4.0E-05	0.04	1.7E-04	0.18
EuF	kg P _{eq}	6.4E-04	9.1E-05	3.0E-04	1.5E-07	8.5E-04	3.9E-05	1.9E-03
EuM	kg N _{eq}	0.03	1.9E-03	0.01	3.2E-06	0.01	8.4E-04	0.04
EuT	mol N _{eq}	0.16	0.02	0.10	3.4E-05	0.06	5.0E-04	0.33
ET	CTUe	3342.24	195.20	213.65	17.65	82.41	16.44	3867.60
LU	Pt	29.73	5.14	2.85	0.00	24.42	0.01	62.15
WU	m ³ depriv.	27.26	0.91	3.04	0.50	2.44	-1.61	32.53
RU-F	MJ	303.49	12.73	616.90	0.05	168.12	0.08	1101.38
RU-MM	kg Sb _{eq}	1.6E-05	5.0E-04	3.6E-05	2.0E-09	2.8E-06	3.1E-09	5.5E-04

CC = Climate change

OD = Ozone depletion

IR = Ionizing radiation

PhOF = Photochemical ozone formation

PM = Particulate matter

HT-NC = Human toxicity, non-cancer

HT-C = Human toxicity, cancer

Ac = Acidification

EuF = Eutrophication, freshwater

EuM = Eutrophication, marine

EuT = Eutrophication, terrestrial

ET = Ecotoxicity

LU = Land use

WU = Water use

RU-F = Resource use, fossils

RU-MM = Resource use, minerals and meta

5. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

To further improve the visibility of the share of impact that each input/output of the CALF-20 synthesis procedure has on its overall impacts, **Figure 3** presents the resulting data in a stacked bar chart, using the same abbreviations key as **Table 7**.

From the chart is clear to see that 1,2,4-triazole supposes the largest share of impact in most categories, even accounting for more than half of the total impact in seven out of sixteen categories.

A clear exception on this trend is the category corresponding to the use of mineral and metallic resources; this is expected, as the component that supposes the largest share in this category is the zinc oxalate precursor, as it comprises the metallic part of the CALF-20 MOF.

Figure 3. Contribution per input/output component to impacts of the CALF-20 synthesis.

Another element to be noted from the chart is that the wastewater output supposes a “negative” impact in the water use category. This is because the “wastewater treatment” item in the Ecoinvent database accounts for avoided impacts in the deprivation of water from natural sources, as it considers the potential reutilization of a fraction of the treated wastewater.

To further visualize the contribution of 1,2,4-triazole as an environmental hotspot to the synthesis of CALF-20, **Figure 4** illustrates the impact network for the process. The network is presented as a Sankey diagram, where the arrows indicate the connection between substances and their precursors, while the widths of the arrows are proportional to the share that the precursor has on the overall impacts of the material that it synthesizes.

Figure 4. Impact network for the synthesis of one kilogram of CALF-20.

The network is generated by SimaPro, where an overall single-score environmental impact is calculated for every element within it. This single-score impact is calculated by the software using the characterization, weighting, and normalization factors of the Environmental Footprint method, making a weighted aggregate of the normalized impacts of every element across all impact categories.

When analyzing the network, it becomes evident that 1,2,4-triazole is the primary contributor to the overall impact of the synthesis procedure – accounting for 57.5% of the overall single-score impact. This suggests that optimizing the consumption of 1,2,4-triazole when synthesizing CALF-20 becomes mandatory to optimize the magnitude of the environmental impacts of the process.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The insights presented in the interpretation of results suppose relevant information that satisfies the general objective of the study, which is to report the environmental impacts of the synthesis of CALF-20, simultaneously providing a baseline for future environmental screenings of CALF-20-enabled technologies, including the SoldAC project.

It is especially important to highlight that when assessing the calculated impacts, 1,2,4-triazole came up as an environmental hotspot, accounting for more than half of the overall impacts of the CALF-20 synthesis procedure. Within the framework of the SoldAC project – and of any other future technology that seeks to implement CALF-20 for CO₂ capture purposes – this information supposes an alert to optimize the use of 1,2,4-triazole when synthesizing the MOF. It then becomes relevant to study intensification techniques on the use of organic synthesis precursors to achieve this optimization at its highest potential.

Future work

It is imperative to thoroughly evaluate the functionality of CALF-20 with respect to its ability for CO₂ uptake. This is key to enable the future development of a future LCA that considers CO₂ uptake as its functional unit, rather than the mass of CALF-20.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was conducted in the context of the project SOLDAC (Full Spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture & Conversion). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. GA 101069359.

REFERENCES

- Cuéllar-Franca, R., García-Gutiérrez, P., Taylor, S., Hardacre, C., & Azapagic, A. (2016). A novel methodology for assessing the environmental sustainability of ionic liquids used for CO₂ capture. *Faraday Discussions*, 192, 283–301. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6FD00054A>
- HengXing Engineering. (n.d.). *Batch Ball Mill*. Despatch Industries. <http://www.hengxingmill.com/products/grinding-mills/99.html>
- ITW EAE. (2020). *LBB Forced Convection Oven*. HengXing Mill. <https://www.despatch.com/pdfs/LBB%20spec%20sheet.pdf>
- Lin, J.-B., Nguyen, T. T. T., Vaidhyanathan, R., Burner, J., Taylor, J. M., Durekova, H., Akhtar, F., Mah, R. K., Ghaffari-Nik, O., Marx, S., Fylstra, N., Iremonger, S. S., Dawson, K. W., Sarkar, P., Hovington, P., Rajendran, A., Woo, T. K., & Shimizu, G. K. H. (2021). A scalable metal-organic framework as a durable physisorbent for carbon dioxide capture. *Science*, 374(6574), 1464–1469. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abi7281>
- Petree, H. E., Pociask, J. R., & Gupton, J. T. (1981). *Method for direct preparation for 1,2,4-triazole from hydrazine and formamide* (Patent No. USA4267347A).

Qi, F., Stein, R. S., & Friščić, T. (2014). Mimicking mineral neogenesis for the clean synthesis of metal–organic materials from mineral feedstocks: coordination polymers, MOFs and metal oxide separation. *Green Chem.*, *16*(1), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3GC41370E>

The European Commission. (2021). Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organizations. *Official Journal of the European Union. Recommendations.*